

PROPOSITIONS TO BE ONE CRITERION TO EVALUATE A READING TEST

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ABSTRACT

The meaning of the sentence is constructed and developed in form of propositions, which forms the scientific basis for identifying sentences with few propositions (simple sentences) or sentences with high proposition density (complex sentences). Propositions play a crucial role in text comprehension and retention. The criteria of compiling texts must consist of the evaluation of proposition density based on the meanings of the sentences. The researcher analyses, identifies and compares the proposition density through the number of meanings of sentences to show a logical evaluation in the texts at the end of junior high school and propose directions for the compilation of texts in the future. The results of this study will contribute new information to the database for compiling texts and the subsequent works.

Keywords: comprehension, meaning, proposition, text, retention.

1 INTRODUCTION

Compiling textbooks is, in general, based on linguistic sciences and meets the development of society in accordance with the policies of the Party and the State. Compilation of English textbooks, in particular, also follows this principle. One of the linguistic bases of English textbooks today is the meaning units of sentences or propositions in sentences. Long or short sentences are not important; however, the important thing is the significant level in the sentence more or less to serve the teaching of the students' level, to help them develop their learning ability. Odd and less meaningful content will make students bored. Therefore, their acquired performance is low.

Advanced countries like the United States, Britain, Australia, etc. use the propositional density as one of the criteria for compiling textbooks. This study meets the current urgent requirement in compiling books, first of all, English textbooks.

The study is based on the method of surveying and analyzing typical sentences in the English high school book series of the National Foreign Language Project 2020 according to the Common European Framework for References. Inductive method is used to put the analysis of scholars' examples into 52 formulas, applied to analyzing propositions in almost all common English sentence patterns.

With the results of the survey and analysis, the study will contribute to the analysis of sentence patterns in English and the compilation of English textbooks later.

2 RATIONALE

The proposition or meaning of the sentence is an important concept for the research on the meaning of the text. T. B. Jay [16] argued that the proposition is a meaningful unit, a statement that represents a practical requirement. According to W. Kintsch [19] and Kintsch & Keenan [17], propositions are a basic unit related to comprehending and retaining texts. "The proposition corresponds to verbs, adjectives, adverbs, prepositions, and conjunctions (not nouns or pronouns)" (M.A. Covington [4]). David Nunan [5] argued that the proposition is a statement of a certain entity or event. A sentence can have a single proposition or multiple propositions.

Usually the proposition is treated as meaning, or is referred to as a more standard term, the semantic content of the sentence and considered the center of the semantics and philosophy of the language (according to Matthew McGrath [20]).

Propositional density is generalized as a measure of the amount of information conveyed and equivalent to the number of words required to express the ideas. The number of words does not determine the number of propositions. Words in expressions, fixed terms or idioms / proverbs are considered a default idea regardless of the number of words. The meaning of idioms or proverbs cannot be guessed by the dictionary meaning (literally) of words and once we understand, their meaning is the default, irreplaceable or incomplementary.

According to James R. Hurford [15], sentences with different structures with identical propositions are called synonyms. In other words, propositions determine the same or different meanings in sentences.

David Nunan conducted a survey and analyzed the following two sentences:

1. Romulus, the legendary founder of Rome, took the women of the Sabine by force. (David, N. 1989: 56)
2. Cleopatra's downfall lay in her fickle trust in the political world. (David, N. 1989: 56)

The two sentences have the same length, but the proposition density in the two sentences is very different.

Analyzing the propositions of sentence 1:

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|---------------------------|
| a. (TOOK, ROMULUS, WOMEN, BY FORCE) | b. (FOUND, ROMULUS, ROME) |
| c. (LEGENDARY, ROMULUS) | d. (SABINE, WOMEN) |

Analyzing the propositions of sentence 2:

- | | |
|------------------------------------|------------------------------|
| a. (BECAUSE, A, B) | b. (FELLDOWN, CLEOPATRA) = A |
| c. (TRUST, CLEOPATRA, FIGURES) = B | d. (FOOLISH, TRUST) |
| e. (FICKLE, FIGURES) | f. (POLITICAL, FIGURES) |
| g. (PART OF, FIGURES, WORLD) | h. (ROMAN, WORLD) |

The two sentences are equivalent in length, but the meaning content of sentence two is twice as many as the one of sentence one. This indicates that sentence two is more complicated than sentence one.

Bealer [2] believes that short or long sentences do not determine the amount of information of the text. It is the high or low proposition density in the sentence that will contain much or less

information that the speaker or writer wants to convey to the reader or listener in different contexts, depending on different levels of acquisition.

The proposition is used by researchers to compare texts. If they do other things, they cannot make comparisons (David Nunan [5]). Many texts have the same length and the same topic shows completely different proposition contents. An experiment of Kintsch and Keenan [17] shows the following: a group of students read two texts of almost the same in length, but the number of propositions varies. They concluded that this group of students understood and remembered text with fewer propositions than text with multiple propositions.

Scott [23] selected two widely used syllabuses for analyzing propositions in 52 randomly selected sentences in each curriculum. The results of this empirical study show that learners easily acquire the textbook with fewer clauses and have difficulty absorbing sentences that contain higher numbers of propositions. Since then, the author proposes that compilation of textbooks must be based on the amount of propositions distributed in sentences that are consistent with students' learning ability.

Scott [23] argues that in different contexts, the number of propositions will affect understanding and the level of acquisition. People with low knowledge base (low level) will absorb low levels of propositions and will have difficulty accessing sentences with high levels of proposition density, whereas those with high knowledge base (high level) will absorb higher levels of propositions easily. Therefore, what needs to be done is to allocate the appropriate number of propositions for each object to access the same amount of knowledge.

Turner and Greene [24] argue that it is necessary to calculate the number of appropriate propositions to compose documents that are suitable for different subjects. Each student or group of students with the same level of competence will absorb texts with a certain proposition density. The text has a very low proposition density which makes learners bored, even if they acquire it. But text has too high propositions that make them difficult to comprehend and retain the knowledge that has just been approached, ie. they cannot absorb it. Atkinson & Shiffrin [1] said that for new learners or students with a low basic level, the initial number of propositions is the lowest and will gradually increase over time in a compatible manner. Appropriate number of propositions will help students to acquire and memorize the amount of information they have learned.

In case the amount of information is too much, surpassing the ability of students to absorb, students will have difficulty in not processing all the information and not fully understand or not remember all the information.

Charmaine DeFrancesco & Kyle Perkins [3] propose that to help students grasp ideas, we can break down information, which means creating many small sentences. This is an effective way to help students understand and apply small amounts of information easily into practice when their background knowledge is still at a low level. The two researchers also came to the conclusion that the proposition density affects students' memory. A too high density leads to short-term memory, on the contrary, a moderate density leads to long-term memory.

According to Truong Ngoc Tuong Linh [25], students with elementary qualifications cannot absorb well-versed sentences with dense propositions. This is beyond the capacity of students and therefore they will understand vaguely and may not even understand them. For higher grades, if the sentence has very few propositional densities, the meaning is too simple, the children will be bored and not interested in learning or reading. Selecting sentences with the density of propositions

The density analysis of propositions s in grade 3 of the Vietnamese text-book.

Quoted:

Hai bàn tay em

Như hoa đầu cành (Huy cận)

Analyzing the propositions:

- a. (BÀN TAY, HAI, EM) = A b. (HAI, BÀN TAY) c. (EM, BÀN TAY)
 d. (HOA, ĐẦU CÀNH) = B e. (NHƯ, A, B)

In grade 3, the sentence has more propositions. The meaning of the sentence is increased to match the higher level of 3rd grade students.

The density analysis of propositions s in grade 4 of the Vietnamese text-book.

Quoted:

Kim tự tháp Ai Cập là lăng mộ của các hoàng đế Ai Cập cổ đại.

Analyzing the propositions:

- a. (AI CẬP, KIM TỰ THÁP) b. (CỬA, LĂNG MỘ, CÁC HOÀNG ĐẾ AI CẬP CỔ ĐẠI)
 c. (LÀ, KIM TỰ THÁP AI CẬP, LĂNG MỘ CỦA CÁC HOÀNG ĐẾ AI CẬP CỔ ĐẠI)
 d. (AI CẬP, CÁC HOÀNG ĐẾ) e. (CỔ ĐẠI, AI CẬP)

Similarly, in grade 4, the propositions of the sentence increase through the increase of the sentence density in the sentence.

The density analysis of propositions s in grade 5 of the Vietnamese text-book.

Quoted:

Ngày hôm nay là ngày khai trường đầu tiên ở nước Việt Nam Dân chủ Cộng hòa. (Hồ Chí Minh)

Analyzing the propositions:

- a. (HÔM NAY, NGÀY)
 b. (KHAI TRƯỜNG, ĐẦU TIÊN, NGÀY)
 c. (LÀ, NGÀY HÔM NAY, NGÀY KHAI TRƯỜNG ĐẦU TIÊN)
 d. (VIỆT NAM DÂN CHỦ CỘNG HÒA, NƯỚC)
 e. (DÂN CHỦ, CỘNG HÒA)
 f. (DÂN CHỦ CỘNG HÒA, VIỆT NAM)
 g. (Ở, NGÀY KHAI TRƯỜNG ĐẦU TIÊN, NƯỚC VIỆT NAM DÂN CHỦ CỘNG HÒA)

At the end of primary school (grade 5), the density of propositions is more to express more complicated ideas.

The meaning of a sentence does not depend on the length or short of the sentence but depends on the number of propositions in the sentence. Modern discourse analysis can analyze sentence propositions to clarify all the ideas in the sentence. Based on the rules for analyzing the density of propositions in sentences, the reader understands clearly the clarity and richness of the language.

When writing books or teaching, we must consider using appropriate propositions so that students can acquire knowledge contained in sentences and accurately translate sentences between the two languages.

The proposition has long been mentioned in semantics and discourse analysis. Foreign scholars have had many works on analyzing propositions in sentences. Through the analysis of some typical sentences in primary Vietnamese books, we find that, although not based on the density of propositions, Vietnamese linguists used logical language to compose textbooks. However, in Vietnam so far there are few or no authors who study and analyze Vietnamese sentences through propositional units. It is thought that it is time for us to do thorough research to see the proposition as a criterion for compiling instructional materials. We are currently not competent to compile the formulas for inducing Vietnamese propositions. The above analysis is based on English formulas as universal formulas in the language. Hopefully, in the near future, Vietnamese linguists will study and shape the propositions in accordance with Vietnamese identity. At that time, when analyzing the meaning of the sentences, we will not use generic words like "few ideas" or "many ideas" but will specify: this sentence has 4 meanings (propositions) or the other has 10 meanings (propositions).

The survey on the sentence patterns of the Junior High School English textbooks

(According to the National Foreign Language Project 2020)

The junior high school English test book set according to the National Foreign Language Project 2020 is chosen as a language for analyzing propositions.

English 6 begins the series of books with simple sentences that have only 1 proposition such as:

Hi, Vy. (P. 6, V. 1, English 6)

1. HI, VY

Are you ready? (P. 6, V. 1, English 6)

1. ARE READY, YOU

The last lesson in volume 1, English 6 also has a simple sentence that includes only one clause:

That's right. (P. 58, V. 1, English 6)

1. IS RIGHT, THAT

Most sentences have a number of propositions of 2, 3, and 4. This is the number of propositions that match the student's A1 level of English learning.

Tet is a time for family gatherings. (P. 58, V. 1, English 6)

1. IS A TIME, TET, FOR WHAT 2. WHAT = GATHERINGS

3. FAMILY, GATHERINGS

Even though it is a complex sentence with a noun clause, the sentence has only four propositions.

Well, the map says Tan Ky House is nearer. (P. 38, V. 1, English 6)

1. WELL 2. SAY, THE MAP, WHAT 3. WHAT = 4

4. IS NEARER, TAN KY HOUSE

However, many sentences have too many propositions right in the first volume of English 6.

I have a new uniform, but I don't wear it every day (only on Mondays and Saturdays). (P. 10, V. 1, English 6)

- | | | |
|-----------------------|---------------------|------------------|
| 1. HAVE, I, A UNIFORM | 2. NEW, UNIFORM | 3. WEAR, I, IT |
| 4. BUT, (1+2) | 5. NEG N'T | 6. WHEN = DAY |
| 7. EVERY DAY | 8. MONDAYS | 9. ONLY, MONDAYS |
| 10. SATURDAYS | 11. ONLY, SATURDAYS | 12. AND, (9+11) |

English 7 consists of sentences with a higher proposition density, usually with 2 or 3 propositions.

I enjoy mountain climbing. (P. 6, V. 1, English 7)

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|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| 1. ENJOY, I, CLIMBING | 2. MOUNTAIN, CLIMBING |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|

They are both really healthy. (P. 16, V. 1, English 7)

- | | | |
|----------------------|---------------|--------------------|
| 1. ARE HEALTHY, THEY | 2. BOTH, THEY | 3. REALLY, HEALTHY |
|----------------------|---------------|--------------------|

Most of the sentences have appropriate levels of propositions of 2, 3, 4 and 5. This density helps students at the beginning of A2 to absorb the lesson without difficulty.

I'm in a mountain climbing club. (P. 6, V. 1, English 7)

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|-------------------|-----------------------|
| 1. AM, I, WHERE | 2. WHERE = IN A CLUB |
| 3. CLIMBING, CLUB | 4. MOUNTAIN, CLIMBING |

In particular, there is a single sentence in this book, but there are too many propositions.

Traditional volunteer activities include raising money for people in need, cooking and giving food, doing general labour (such as clean-up projects and home repair), providing transportation (such as giving rides to the elderly), and tutoring/mentoring young people.

(P. 32, V. 1, English 7)

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|---------------------------------|--------------------------------|
| 1. INCLUDE, ACTIVITIES, RAISING | 2. TRADITIONAL, ACTIVITIES |
| 3. VOLUNTEER, ACTIVITIES | 4. MONEY, RAISING |
| 5. FOR, MONEY, PEOPLE | 6. IN NEED, PEOPLE |
| 7. INCLUDE, ACTIVITIES, COOKING | 8. INCLUDE, ACTIVITIES, GIVING |
| 9. FOOD, COOKING | 10. FOOD, GIVING |
| 11. LABOUR, DOING | 12. GENERAL, LABOUR |
| 13. SUCH AS | 14. CLEAN-UP, PROJECTS |
| 15. HOME, REPAIR | 16. TRANSPORTATION, PROVIDING |
| 17. SUCH AS | 18. RIDES, GIVING |
| 19. TO THE ELDERLY | 20. PEOPLE, TUTORING |
| 21. PEOPLE, MENTORING | 22. YOUNG, PEOPLE |

Volume 1, English 8, has many sentences with simple propositions like the following sentences:

Stop reading comics! (P. 6, V. 1, English 8)

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|-------------------------|------------------------|
| 1. STOP, (YOU), READING | 2. READ, (YOU), COMICS |
|-------------------------|------------------------|

However, in this book there are sentences with very high proposition densities:

They prefer watching TV and playing computer games to reading books, perhaps because they don't have to think and imagine as much. (P. 12, V. 1, English 8)

- | | |
|---------------------------|---------------------------|
| 1. PREFER, THEY, WATCHING | 2. WATCHING, (THEY), TV |
| 3. PREFER, THEY, PLAYING | 4. PLAYING, (THEY), GAMES |
| 5. COMPUTER, GAMES | 6. READING, (THEY), BOOKS |
| 7. TO, 2 + 4 + 6 | 8. PERHAPS |
| 9. BECAUSE, 7 + 15 | 10. HAVE TO THINK, THEY |
| 11. NEG N'T | 12. HAVE TO IMAGINE, THEY |
| 13. NEG N'T | 14. AS MUCH |
| | 15. AND, 10 + 12 |

At the end of the junior high school level or level A2 according to the Common European Framework for References, English 9, the first volume, including sentences with at least two propositions:

That must be a memorable experience. (P. 6, V. 1, English 9)

- | | |
|------------------------------|--------------------------|
| 1. MUST BE, THAT, EXPERIENCE | 2. MEMORABLE, EXPERIENCE |
|------------------------------|--------------------------|

I really like the photo exhibition. (P. 60, V. 1, English 9)

- | | | |
|------------------------|----------------|----------------------|
| 1. LIKE, I, EXHIBITION | 2. RALLY, LIKE | 3. PHOTO, EXHIBITION |
|------------------------|----------------|----------------------|

However, many sentences have too high proposition density:

They say that a city's green space, urban sprawl, natural features, cultural attractions, convenience, and pollution should be added to the list. (P. 22, V. 1, English 9)

- | | |
|---------------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| 1. SAY, THEY, THAT | 2. THAT = (6 + 8 + 10 + 12 + 13) |
| 3. SHOULD BE, SPACE, ADDED | 4. GREEN, SPACE |
| 5. CITY'S, SPACE | 6. SHOULD BE, SPRAWL, ADDED |
| 7. URBAN, SPRAWL | 8. SHOULD BE, FEATURES, ADDED |
| 9. NATURAL, FEATURES | 10. SHOULD BE, ATTRACTIONS, ADDED |
| 11. CULTURAL, ATTRACTIONS | 12. SHOULD BE, CONVENIENCE, ADDED |
| 13. SHOULD BE, POLLUTION, ADDED | 14. TO THE LIST |

These high proposition density sentences must be dealt with to help students acquire the information in the course.

3 ASSESSMENT BASED ON LINGUISTICS ON PROPOSITIONS

Through the survey and analysis of the proposition density of sentences in the Junior High School English textbooks under the National Foreign Language Project 2020, we draw the following remarks:

Most of the sentences in the series have a propositional density appropriate to the level of English learners from grades 6 to 9. Simple proposition densities are distributed in English books 6 with one or more sentence propositions. This density increases gradually in English 7. In English 8, the

texts have very few sentences containing one or two clauses. In particular, grade 9 English book only has sentences that contain two or more propositions. In the last two volumes of Junior High School English, the density is highly recommended to help students prepare for the high school final exams and entrance exams for senior high school.

The density of propositions is simple and medium, helping students absorb and memorize the amount of information in the course.

The following survey summarizes the simple and average proposition analysis in the above four volumes (See Appendix 1).

4 SOLUTION TO THE CASES OF UNUSUALLY HIGH PROPOSITION DENSITY

According to Charmaine DeFrancesco & Kyle Perkins [3], sentences with unusually high proposition densities make it difficult for students to absorb and remember. The author proposes to retend the idea of the sentence proposition, but the sentence must be reduced to single sentences with a moderate or higher average density. Moderate proposition density will be appropriate for students' learning level.

On this basis, we propose to break down the highly advanced propositions in the surveyed sentences as follows:

English 6, volume 1:

I have a new uniform, but I don't wear it every day (only on Mondays and Saturdays). (P. 10, V. 1, English 6)

This sentence should be rewritten as follows: I have a new uniform, but I don't wear it every day. I wear it only on Mondays and Saturdays.

- | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------|
| 1. HAVE, I, A UNIFORM | 2. NEW, UNIFORM |
| 3. WEAR, I, IT | 4. BUT, (1+2) |
| 5. NEG N'T | 6. WHEN = DAY |
| 7. EVERY DAY | |

And:

- | | |
|----------------------|---------------------|
| 1. WEAR, I, IT, WHEN | 2. WHEN = MONDAYS |
| 3. ONLY, MONDAYS | 4. WHEN = SATURDAYS |
| 5. ONLY, SATURDAYS | |

The breakdown of the sentence above still ensures the amount of information, but the density of propositions in each sentence becomes consistent with the level of the acquisition of students.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Previously the proposition was not evaluated correctly. From the point of view of the systemic functional grammar, the proposition plays an important role in determining the meaning density of the sentence, thus affecting the amount of information in the text. When drafting text, in general, or compiling textbooks, in particular, the editor must carefully consider the density of the sentence proposition. Textbooks aiming at students at different grade levels and different knowledge and

acquisition levels must have appropriate propositions. The progress of linguistics has helped us calculate the specific number of propositions in each sentence. This is an optimal tool to help distribute the amount of information / meaning conveyed to students.

The set of the junior high school English books according to the National Foreign Language Project 2020 is compiled based on the Common European Framework for References at Level A2 (KET), so the distribution of simple propositions (1, 2 and 3) and moderate (3, 4, 5, 6 and 7) exist in most texts. This is an advantage of the textbooks, meeting one of the scientific criteria for language when compiling textbooks to meet the development stage and the competence level of students and to help students acquire optimal amount of knowledge. However, many sentences have abnormally high proposition densities like 9, 12, and 14 in English 6; 9, 11, and even 22 in English 7; 13, 15, and 16 in English 8; 14, 15, 16, and even 21 in English 9. In the syllabus, the first volume is for the first semester and the second volume is for the second semester and according to the learning progress, the amount of knowledge in the first semester must be lower than the one in the other semester. But the shortcoming is that sometimes the book for the first semester has more sentences than the one in the other semester. This is unreasonable and unsuitable for the student's development period and acquisition capacity, thus making it difficult for students to continue the lesson. This should be avoided when compiling a standard textbook set at the national level for students.

Based on the survey and proposition density analysis in typical sentences in the above junior high school English textbooks, we offer the following suggestions:

- Proposition density must be considered one of the scientific criteria for compiling textbooks.
- Density of propositions must be consistent with the competence of students: simple at a low level, increasing in accordance with progress and high at the level appropriate to the development of students.
- Improving the number of propositions when students are at a high level.
- At low levels, limiting or not distributing high proposition density sentences by breaking them into single sentences or compound sentences and complex sentences with few propositions so that the amount of information does not change.

Next research proposals

All works have the next research direction due to the necessity of expansion or objective and subjective restrictions.

We propose further research focusing on the following issues:

- Density of propositions in sentences affects learner's age.
- Density of propositions in sentences affects the knowledge background of learners.
- Density of propositions in sentences affects the gender of learners.
- Density of propositions in the sentence affects the social position of learners.
- Density of propositions in sentences affects the locality of learners.
- How native language, second language and foreign language affect proposition density.
- How types of documents affect the acquisition of propositional density in sentences.

- The proposition contains abstract words that are different from the proposition that contains specific and simple words.
- Researching and compiling the proposition formulas for Vietnamese to properly evaluate the meaning of the Vietnamese identity.

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